

Full Length Research Paper

The supplementary effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water on performance and blood indices of finisher broilers

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An experiment was conducted to investigate the effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water (MOLW) on the performance and blood indices of finisher broilers. Varying proportions of *Moringa oleifera* fresh leaves 50 g, 150 g and 250 g, respectively, for T₂, T₃, and T₄ were each boiled in 20 litres of water and allowed to cool to obtain *Moringa oleifera* leaf water (MOLW). Four groups of fifteen broiler chicks (28 days old) of Agrited breed were randomly assigned to one of the *Moringa oleifera* leaf water for 28 days in a completely randomized design. Each group was subdivided into three replicates of five birds each. The birds were fed normal broiler finisher diet for all the groups. At the end of the *Moringa oleifera* leaf water intake trial for 28 days, results showed that average body weight changes and average daily body weight gain increased significantly at T₃ (150 g/20 litre H₂O) compared to other treatments. There was no significant difference (P > 0.05) on the average daily water intake, average daily feed intake and feed conversion

ratio. The haemoglobin and neutrophils decreased (P < 0.05) as the concentration of *Moringa oleifera* leaf in the *Moringa oleifera* leaf water (MOLW) increased. Conversely, the lymphocytes increased (P < 0.05) as the concentration of MOLW increased in the treatments. The biochemical values showed that total serum protein, globulin and urea decreased significantly (P < 0.05) as the inclusion level of the *Moringa oleifera* leaf in *moringa oleifera* leaf water increased. Serum creatinine increased significantly (P < 0.05) at T₃ (150 g *Moringa* leaf/20 litres of H₂O). It was finally concluded that water from cooked *Moringa oleifera* leaf can be used to improve growth performance of finisher broiler birds at 150 g/20 litres of water without any deleterious effect on the blood indices of the birds.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, boiled water, broiler finishers, performance, blood indices

INTRODUCTION

The need to improve on the growth and liveability of broilers is becoming very urgent due to the need to produce healthy table meat within a short period of time for the increasing population of mankind. Often times, most feed formulated for broilers may be theoretically balanced but not nutritionally adequate due to lack of essential nutrients necessary for growth and good health. The implication is the purchase of exorbitant synthetic nutrients fortified with vitamins, minerals and some essential amino acids to enhance the nutritional status of

the animals which adds to the cost of production and consequently high cost of broiler meat.

Moringa oleifera leaves have the potential to supply some needed nutrients for the growth of broilers and reduce the cost of supplementary synthetic nutrients. Armelle and Melarie, (2010) reported that *Moringa oleifera* leaves are nutritionally rich and an excellent source of concentrated protein, vitamins and minerals. This plant is grown in almost every home in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria and very much available. Nihad et

al. (2016) reported the proximate composition of *Moringa oleifera* to contain 5.89% ash, 17.41% fibre, 25.37% protein, 2.44% lipid and 39.02% total sugars and similarly, it was reported that the proximate and mineral composition of *Moringa oleifera* leaves contained 6.00% ash, 2.43% crude fat, 5.43% crude fibre, 39.13% crude protein, 38.21% carbohydrate, 23.20mg/100g K, 214.00 mg/100g Na, 723 mg/100g Ca, 677.00 mg/100g Mg, 5.00 mg/100 g P, 187 Mg/100g Fe, 252 mg/100g Mn, 55 mg/100g Cu and 548 mg/100g of Zn (Sodamade *et al.*, 2013). The values reported is an indication that *Moringa oleifera* leaves are nutritionally rich and could serve as supplements in broiler diets. Tijani *et al.* (2016) reported that *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal improved weight gain and feed conversion ratio at 15% dietary inclusion level. *Moringa oleifera* leaf has been successfully used in broiler rations either as leaf meal (Gadzirayi *et al.*, 2012; Onunkwo and George, 2015) or by aqueous extraction from the leaf meal (Alabi *et al.*, 2017; Mona and Elbestawy, 2017) to feed broilers and improve on their performance. However, there is no information on the use of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water on broilers by cooking to boil. The objective of this study therefore, was to evaluate the performance and broiler indices of broiler finishers placed on *Moringa oleifera* leaf water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This experiment was carried out at the poultry unit of teaching and research farm, Imo State University Owerri, which is located within the South-Eastern agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. Owerri lies between latitude 5°29'North and longitude 7°20'East. It is about 91m above sea level with annual rainfall, temperature and humidity ranging from 1,500mm to 2,200 mm, 20.0 – 27.5°C and 75 – 90%, respectively (Accuweather, 2015).

Source and processing of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water (MOLW)

The *Moringa* leaves used in this study were freshly obtained from Imo State University Research and Demonstration Farm, Owerri. The leaves were weighed at a given proportion of 50 g, 150 g, 250 g respectively, for T₂, T₃, and T₄. Each of the treatment leaf meal was boiled in 20 liters of water and allowed to cool. This was served to the experimental birds as their drinking water at a given equal volume for T₂, T₃, and T₄, while T₁ which was the control received normal drinking water. Initially, Fresh *Moringa* leaf was dried, ground into a fine powder and sent to the laboratory for analysis according to AOAC, (2000). The metabolizable energy (ME) was calculated according to the method of Ponzenga, (1985). $ME = (37 \times \text{Crude Protein}) + (81.8 \times \text{Ether Extract}) + (35.5 \times \text{Nitrogen Free Extract})$.

Experimental diets

The birds on all the treatments were fed on the same normal diet containing 19.0% crude protein and 2800 Kcal/kg of metabolizable energy. Each of the treatment groups was supplemented with the *Moringa oleifera* leaf water (MOLW) which contained 50 g, 150 g and 250 g *Moringa oleifera* leaves per 20 litres of water during the cooking extraction respectively for T₂, T₃ and T₄. These *Moringa oleifera* leaf water served as their drinking water for the four weeks of the trial. T₁ or the control was served normal water.

Experimental birds and design

60 day old broiler chicks were purchased from a certified poultry vendor in Owerri. The chicks were brood for four (4) weeks and fed commercial diet. Thereafter, the birds were divided into four (4) groups of 15 birds each in a completely randomized design. Each group was further subdivided into three replicates of five birds per replicate. Each of the groups was assigned to one of the three treatment *Moringa oleifera* leaf water while T₁ (control) had normal water. The *Moringa oleifera* leaf water was prepared and replaced for all the treatments as soon as the 20 litres of any treatment is finished. The initial live weight of the birds was taken using a weighing scale and recorded. Thereafter, the weight of the birds was taken on weekly bases. The birds were fed *ad libitum*. Clean fresh drinking water was supplied to the birds in treatment one as the control. Feeding trial lasted for four weeks.

Data collection

Feed intake was recorded daily and the birds weighed weekly after taking the initial body weight. Feed intake was determined by weighing the feed offered and the left-over the following day. The difference between the two values was the feed consumed. Feed conversion ratio was determined by dividing average daily feed intake by average daily body weight gain. Water intake was recorded daily. Water intake was determined by weighing the *Moringa* leaf water offered and the left-over the following day. The difference between the two values was taken as the *Moringa oleifera* leaf water intake.

Haematology and blood biochemistry

At the last day of the feeding trial, three layers per treatment were randomly selected to determine the haematological and serum biochemical indices of the birds. Blood samples were collected from the wing web of the birds using syring and needle and placed in the

Table 1. Proximate composition of *Moringa oleifera* leaf.

Parameters	Composition (%DM)
Dry matter	93.05
Moisture	6.95
Ether extract	6.45
Crude protein	23.42
Crude fibre	16.21
Ash	10.03
Nitrogen free extract	36.94
Metabolizable energy (Kcal/Kg)	2705.52

Table 2. Performance of experimental finisher broilers offered varying concentration of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water.

Parameters	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	SEM
Average initial weight (g)	620.80	625.00	620.50	633.20	5.10
Average final weight (g)	1458.30	1429.20	1597.20	1433.30	48.97
Average body weight change (g)	837.50 ^b	804.17 ^b	976.37 ^a	800.00 ^b	34.22
Average daily weight gain (g)	29.93 ^b	28.73 ^b	34.90 ^a	28.57 ^b	1.23
Average daily feed intake (g)	105.43	104.03	115.17	105.00	3.96
Average daily MOLW intake (ml)	326.67	317.87	325.67	319.53	2.92
Feed conversion ratio	3.53	3.68	3.33	3.70	0.21

Ab Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different

Note: T₁ = T₁ (control / Normal water)

T₂ = T₂ (50g Moringa leaf/ 20 litres of H₂O)

T₃ = T₃ (150g Moringa leaf/ 20 litres of H₂O)

T₄ = T₄ (250g Moringa leaf/ 20 litres of H₂O)

specimen bottles with EDTA (Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetate) for haematological studies. Blood was analysed within three hours of collection for haemoglobin (HB), packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell (RBC), mean cell volume (MCV), mean cell haemoglobin (MCH), mean cell haemoglobin concentration (MCHC), and white blood cell (WBC) as outlined by Ochie and Kolhatkar, (2000). Blood samples placed in the specimen bottles without EDTA was used to analyse the serum biochemical parameters such as urea, total protein, creatinine, and cholesterol as outlined by Ochie and Kolhatkar, (2000).

Statistical analysis

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance using the SPSS software (2012). Where analysis of variance indicated significant treatment effects, means were compared using Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT) (SPSS, 2012)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate composition of *Moringa oleifera* leaf

The proximate composition of MOLW is shown in (Table 1). The crude protein, crude fibre, ether extract and ash

were close to the values 23.80% crude protein, 16.57% crude fibre, 5.50% ether extract and 9.75% ash reported by Alabi *et al.* (2017) and 15.51% crude fibre, 24.80% crude protein, 7.11% ether extract reported by Debebe and Eyobel, (2017). However, the values were at variance with 39.13% crude protein, 5.45% crude fibre and 2.43% crude fat reported by Sodamade *et al.* (2013). The values revealed in this research indicate that *Moringa oleifera* leaf is rich in protein and could serve as a protein supplement or feed additive to enhance growth of animals.

Performance of the experimental finisher broiler birds

Data on the performance of the experimental birds are presented in (Table 2). There were no significant treatment effect ($P > 0.05$) on the average daily water intake, average daily feed intake and feed conversion ratio. Average body weight change and average daily weight gain significantly increased ($P < 0.05$) at T₃ (150 g Moringa leaf/ 20 litres of H₂O). The value of the feed conversion ratio was also best at T₃ (150 g Moringa leaf/ 20 litres of H₂O) of *Moringa oleifera* leaf water intake. It is evident from the results that dietary intake of MOLW at the concentration of 150 g/20 litres of H₂O enhanced average daily weight gain and better feed conversion ratio. In the same vein, Alabi *et al.* (2017) reported that

Table 3. Haematological indices of finisher broilers offered *Moringa oleifera* leaf water.

Parameters	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	SEM
HB (g/dl)	12.90 ^a	12.64 ^{ab}	12.04 ^{ab}	11.79 ^b	0.35
PCV (%)	41.97	39.30	36.97	35.64	1.86
RBC (X10 ¹² /l)	12.94	12.27	11.80	11.54	0.60
MCV (fl)	32.43	32.04	31.90	31.24	0.54
MCH (pg)	10.00	10.30	10.17	10.20	0.11
MCHC (g/dl)	30.80	32.30	32.63	31.43	0.76
WBC (x10 ⁹ /l)	11.57	11.47	11.43	11.37	0.15
Neutrophils (%)	56.64 ^a	52.65 ^b	53.97 ^{ab}	53.30 ^{ab}	0.15
Lymphocytes (%)	40.37 ^b	44.30 ^a	42.37 ^{ab}	43.37 ^{ab}	0.88
Basophil (%)	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
Monocytes (%)	1.52	1.87	2.20	1.87	0.29

Ab Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different.

Table 4. Biochemical indices of finisher broilers offered *Moringa oleifera* leaf water.

Parameters	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	SEM
Urea (Mmole/l)	7.97 ^a	6.84 ^b	6.27 ^b	6.57 ^b	0.19
Creatine (Mmole/l)	55.64 ^b	72.97 ^{ab}	76.64 ^a	62.64 ^{ab}	5.00
Cholesterol (Mmole/l)	7.64 ^a	7.07 ^b	7.04 ^b	6.97 ^b	0.11
Total protein (g/dl)	63.27 ^a	59.27 ^b	57.64 ^{bc}	54.64 ^c	1.01
Albumin (g/dl)	19.99	21.66	19.99	21.99	1.01
Globulin (g/dl)	43.28 ^a	37.65 ^b	37.65 ^b	32.65 ^b	1.59
Sodium (Mmole/l)	43.00 ^a	40.00 ^a	40.30 ^a	39.67 ^b	1.18
Potassium (Mmole/l)	1.27	1.13	1.20	1.03	0.13
HCO ₃ (Mmole/l)	11.27	10.83	10.97	10.73	0.29
Chloride (Mmole/l)	24.00 ^a	21.00 ^b	21.33 ^b	21.00 ^b	0.60
ALK (iu/l)	1.35	1.21	1.15	1.18	0.06
SGOT (iu/l)	11.77	11.33	11.33	11.73	0.25
SGPT (iu/l)	6.58	6.85	7.08	6.78	0.17

Abc Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different.

aqueous *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract improved feed conversion efficiency at 90 ml/litre in drinking water. Similarly, Tijani *et al.* (2016) reported similarity in feed intake while the weight gain was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) at 15% dietary intake of *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal in broiler finishers. Nihad *et al.* (2016) also reported increase in body weight of broilers at 15% and 20% dietary level of *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal. The heavier body weight gain of broilers that drank the MOLW at the concentration of 150 g/20 litres of H₂O could be attributed to a likely higher intake of amino acids (Tijani *et al.*, 2016). Chickens offered MOLW at T₄ (250 g Moringa leaf/20 litres of H₂O) showed reduced weight gain compared to T₃ (150 g Moringa leaf/ 20litres of H₂O). The reduced weight gain could be attributed to a higher intake of tannin, phytate and oxalate leading to nutrient imbalance and poor metabolism (Iheukwumere *et al.*, 2008; Tijani *et al.*, 2016).

Haematological and serum biochemical indices

Data on haematological and serum biochemical indices of broiler finishers supplied with dietary MOLW are presented in (Tables 3 and 4). The results showed that haemoglobin (HB), neutrophils and lymphocytes were affected by treatments ($P < 0.05$). The haemoglobin and neutrophils decreased ($P < 0.05$) as the concentration of *Moringa oleifera* leaf in the MOLW increased. Conversely, the lymphocytes increased as the concentration of MOLW increased in the treatments. Haemoglobin was significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) at T₄ (250 g *Moringa* leaf/20 litres of H₂O) MOLW concentration. In a similar study with chickens, increasing inclusion level of *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the haemoglobin and other haematological indices (Tijani *et al.*, 2015). This reduction could be attributed to anti-nutritional factors present in

Moringa oleifera leaf. Akanji, (2002) reported a positive correlation between tannin, phytate and oxalate intakes and HB and RBC values in broiler chickens fed bambara groundnut. The values obtained from this study were higher than the values (5.53 – 8.30g/dl) reported by Tijani *et al.* (2015) for chickens fed diet containing *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal. HB ranged from 11.77 to 12.90g/dl and within the normal range (11.60 – 13.68g/dl) (Wikivet, 2013).

This implies that within this concentration of MOLW intake, the haemoglobin is still adequate to perform its function of conveying oxygen to the cells and transporting carbon dioxide from the cell back to the blood. The packed cell volume (PCV) ranged from 35.64 to 41.97%. There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) on the treatments indicating that the MOLW intake did not pose any threat on the health and physiological functioning of the blood at these levels. The value of PCV obtained from this study were higher than the value 16.67 – 25.00% and 29.91- 31.79% reported by Tijani *et al.* (2015) and Nihad *et al.* (2016) respectively, for broilers fed *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal and within the normal range (35.9 – 41.0%) (Merck, 2012; Wikivet, 2013). A decrease in PCV was suggestive of liver and kidney disease (Demoranville and Best, 2013).

The red blood cell (RBC), mean cell volume (MCV), mean cell haemoglobin (MCH) and mean cell haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) did not show any significant difference ($P > 0.05$) among treatments. Low values of HB and RBC were a good sign of emerging anaemia (Mohammed and Oloyede, 2009). The RBC values showed that the MOLW did not contaminate the blood of the broiler chicken as to cause any health hazards or to reduce the transport of gases in and out of the tissues to and fro the blood. The white blood cells (WBC), eosinophil, basophil, and monocyte did not show any significant treatment effect ($P > 0.05$). The neutrophil decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) at T₂, 50g/20 litres *Moringa oleifera* leaf water concentration. However, T₁ (control), T₃ (150g/20 litres of H₂O) and T₄ (250 g/20 litres of H₂O) were statistically similar ($P > 0.05$). Neutrophils are walls of defence against bacteria in the tissues and their number increases when acute infection is present (Banerjee, 2013).

The implication of the values of the neutrophils, lymphocytes and white blood cells is that MOLW at this level of inclusion did not cause any physiological disharmony in the blood of the chicken. The biochemical values showed that serum urea, creatinine, cholesterol and total protein were affected by treatments ($P < 0.05$). Total serum protein and globulin decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) as the inclusion level of the *Moringa oleifera* leaf in *moringa oleifera* leaf water increased. Serum protein and globulin decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) with the intake of the MOLW compared to the control. This is similar to the findings of Tijani *et al.* (2015) who reported decrease in serum protein for broilers fed

Moringa leaf meal.

A decrease in serum protein could be due to interference on normal protein metabolism (Bolu and Balogun, 2009). This protein metabolism interference could be attributed to presence of residual anti-nutritional factors in *Moringa* leaf. *Moringa* leaf has phytotoxins such as lecithin, alkaloids, tannins, oxalate and phytate (Odetola, 2012).

The values of serum protein (54.64 – 63.27) were higher than 38.74 – 43.05 obtained by Tijani *et al.* (2015) on broilers fed *Moringa* leaf meal but lower than 60.06 – 72.36 obtained by Jiwuba *et al.* (2016) for rabbits fed *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal. Sanchez Monge *et al.* (2004) reported that increased globulins are seen in chronic infections, liver damage and kidney dysfunction. Serum albumin is a strong predictor of health; a low albumin concentration is a sign of poor health (Kastow, 2009). The decreased values of the globulin were an indicator that the healths of the birds were very intact with the MOLW at these levels. The serum urea concentration decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) with the increasing concentration of *Moringa* in treatments. Jiwuba *et al.* (2016) made a similar observation on rabbits fed *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal and Agbabiaka *et al.* (2013) on broiler finishers fed raw tiger nuts based diets. However, this is contrary to the observations of Tijani *et al.* (2015) who reported increased uric acid for broilers fed *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal.

High level of serum urea was an indication of low protein quality as a result of imbalance of amino acids (Nworgu *et al.*, 2007). Significant reduction in serum urea for the MOLW treatments was an indication of good quality protein. It then means that MOLW impacted positively on the protein quality of the blood. Serum creatinine increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) at T₃ (150 g *Moringa* leaf/20 litres of H₂O). The values ranged from 55.64 - 76.64 Mmole/l. Excess creatinine in the blood is from muscle when wasting occurs and creatinine phosphate is catabolised (Yuengang *et al.*, 2008). T₃ (150 g *Moringa* leaf/20 litres of H₂O) was significantly increased compared to the control.

High serum creatinine concentration was a sign of protein insufficiency. This could be due to interference in amino acid metabolism as a result of anti-nutritional factors in the *Moringa* leaf. Serum cholesterol decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) at the MOLW treatments compared to the control. Similar observation were made by Jiwuba *et al.* (2016) on rabbits fed *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal and Ghassi *et al.* (2000) on winstar rats fed crude extracts of *Moringa oleifera* leaf in high fat diet.

This could imply that *Moringa* leaf water intake is hypocholesterolemic. In other words, fat was mobilized to the tissue and utilized.

This observation could be of great economic importance in the production of meat with low fat content. The enzymes ALK, SGOT and SGPT were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) suggesting that the

organs and protein quality were not compromised by the presence of anti-nutrients in the MOLW (Esiegwu, 2017).

Conclusion

The study revealed that *Moringa oleifera* leaf water intake improved performance at the concentration of 150 g of Moringa leaf to 20 litres of water without any negative effect. There was no toxic effect on the blood indices measured. It is therefore recommended that *Moringa oleifera* leaf water for broiler chicken be included at 150 g/20 litres of H₂O.

Author's declaration

I declared that this study is an original research that was carried out by me and I agree to publish it in the journal.

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